

Figure 2: Computation tree of the number of models up to $n = 4$

p	cnf	2n	(n-1)*4+2
a	1	...	n 0
e	n+1	...	2n 0
-1		-2	-(n+2) 0
-1		2	(n+2) 0
1		-2	(n+2) 0
1		2	-(n+2) 0
-(n+2)		-3	-(n+3) 0
-(n+2)		3	(n+3) 0
(n+2)		-3	(n+3) 0
(n+2)		3	-(n+3) 0
.		.	.
.		.	.
-(2n-1)		-n	-2n 0
-(2n-1)		n	2n 0
(2n-1)		-n	2n 0
(2n-1)		n	-2n 0
(n+1)		2n	0
-(n+1)		-2n	0

Figure 3: Equality True - QDIMACS formula

2.2 Model Count

The alternating quantifier structure breaks the symmetries of the formula to some extent, however it is still possible to describe the model counting using alternating sums and squares. This relation can also be described using a recursive approach. This recursion becomes apparent by displaying the computation graphically as in figure 2.

The full model count can be computed by the recursion

$$\#models(n) = (\#models(n-1) + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} (2^i - 1 + 2^{i+1} - 1)^2)^2.$$

3 Parity True

The formulas of the family *ParityTrue* [Heisinger and Seidl, 2023] encode the constraint $((x_1 \oplus \dots \oplus x_n) \oplus y)$ with prefix $\forall x_1 \dots x_n \exists y \exists z_2 \dots z_n$ resulting in clauses (with $2 < i \leq n$)

$$\begin{array}{ll} (\bar{z}_2 \vee x_1 \vee x_2) & (\bar{z}_2 \vee \bar{x}_1 \vee \bar{x}_2) \\ (z_2 \vee \bar{x}_1 \vee x_2) & (z_2 \vee x_1 \vee \bar{x}_2) \\ (\bar{z}_i \vee z_{i-1} \vee x_i) & (\bar{z}_i \vee \bar{z}_{i-1} \vee \bar{x}_i) \\ (z_i \vee \bar{z}_{i-1} \vee x_i) & (z_i \vee z_{i-1} \vee \bar{x}_i) \\ (y \vee z_n) & (\bar{y} \vee \bar{z}_n) \end{array}$$

The variables z_i are Tseitin variables whose values are fixed by the values of the universal variables.

3.1 Structure

For a given size parameter n the formula has n universal and n existential variables. Additionally to the $4(n-1)$ clauses used for encoding the XORs, two clauses are used for control variables. Independently to the parameter n the formulas of this family have two quantifier blocks.

The formula pattern in QDIMACS format is displayed in figure 3.

3.2 Model Count

The encoded XOR structure of the formula enforces that each sub-tree of the formula has exactly one true path. This also implies that the total model count is equal to one independently of the parameter n .

The full model count is represented by the constant function:

$$\#models(n) = 1.$$

4 KBKF Formula Families

Formulas of the KBKF family [Kleine Büning *et al.*, 1995] are known to cause an exponential increase in complexity for Q-Resolution proofs and consequently are difficult to solve for QCDCL solvers. In [Heisinger and Seidl, 2023] a true version has been presented based on negation and Plaisted-Greenbaum Normal form transformation. We modify this encoding to a Tseitin Transformation.

The matrix consists of the following clauses:

$$\begin{array}{ll} y_1 & \leftrightarrow (d_1 \wedge e_1) \\ y_{2j} & \leftrightarrow (\bar{d}_j \wedge \bar{x}_j \wedge d_{j+1} \wedge e_{j+1}) \\ y_{2j+1} & \leftrightarrow (\bar{e}_j \wedge x_j \wedge d_{j+1} \wedge e_{j+1}) \\ y_{2n} & \leftrightarrow (\bar{d}_n \wedge \bar{x}_n \wedge f_1 \wedge \dots \wedge f_n) \\ y_{2n+1} & \leftrightarrow (\bar{e}_n \wedge x_n \wedge f_1 \wedge \dots \wedge f_n) \\ z_{2j} & \leftrightarrow (x_j \wedge \bar{f}_j) \\ z_{2j-1} & \leftrightarrow (\bar{x}_j \wedge f_j) \\ (y_1 \vee \dots \vee y_{2n+1} \vee z_1 \vee \dots \vee z_{2n}) & \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} 1 \leq j \leq n-1 \\ 1 \leq j \leq n \end{array}$$

with prefix

$$\forall d_1 e_1 \exists x_1 \forall d_2 e_2 \exists x_2 \dots \forall d_n e_n \exists x_n \forall f_1 \dots f_n \exists y_1 \dots y_{2n+1} z_1 \dots z_{2n}$$

4.1 Structure

For a given size parameter n the formula has $3n$ universal and $n + 4(n-1) + 5$ existential variables. The number of

83 clauses can be calculated by $13n + (n - 1)$ for Kleine Büning
84 True (resp. $18n$ for Kleine Büning Tseitin). The number of
85 quantifier blocks is $4 + 2(n - 1)$.

86 4.2 Model Count

The full model count for the KBKFTrueTseitin formulas can
be computed by

$$\#models(n) = \left(2^{\frac{4 \cdot 4^n - 3 \cdot 3^n - 1}{6}}\right)^2,$$

87 where $\frac{4 \cdot 4^n - 3 \cdot 3^n - 1}{6}$ describes the n -th generalized Poly-
88 Bernoulli number. This number reflects how many of the
89 Tseitin variables are true in each branch. For the original
90 KBKFTrue formulas, there are more choices for the labels
91 because of the Plaisted Greenbaum transformation (implica-
92 tion instead of bi-implication). Hence, a similar argument as
93 given for the EqualityTrue formulas apply for calculating the
94 total count.

95 References

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